

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Shodiya Otanazarova

THE IMAGE OF LAYLI AND MAJNUN IN ALISHER NAVOI'S EPIC "SADDI ISKANDARIY"

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/IYUL

★ ★ ★ ★ ★
HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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